

Condensation of Chloral with Acid Amides. Properties of $-\text{CH}(\text{OH})\cdot\text{CCl}_3$ Group.

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The present paper deals with the reduction by zinc and glacial acetic acid of the condensation products of chloral with some aliphatic and aromatic acid amides. The formula given by Yelburgi and Wheeler (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 1) is applied to the products.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of the Amides with Chloral.—Chloral (a little excess over the molecular proportion) and the amides were mixed. The reaction was vigorous with acetamide, but with other amides the mixture required to be heated at 100° . The higher products are sticky. Excess of chloral and the unreacted amides were removed by triturating the solid with cold water. The product was crystallised from dilute alcohol.

Reduction of the Chloral Amides.—Zinc dust (2 mol.) was added gradually under stirring during 4-5 hours below 40° to the chloral amide in acetic acid. Zinc acetate began to separate as the reduction progressed and addition of more acetic acid was advisable to facilitate stirring. Finally zinc acetate was filtered off. With *isobutyramide*, *phenylacetamide* and *benzamide*, the filtrate gave the solid on dilution with water. It was then further purified. With other amides the filtrate was neutralised with caustic soda solution of moderate strength at below 40° . The product separated as an oil. If it did not solidify it was extracted with ether and distilled under reduced pressure. These products are soluble in cold and hot water and in most organic solvents. They are stable and distil without decomposition.

The properties of the new compounds are given in the following table.

Name.	Formula.	Crystallised from.	Appearance.	M.p.	Analysis	
					Found.	Calc.
β -Dichlorovinylacetamide	... $C_4H_5ONCl_2$	Dilute alcohol	Rectangular plates	88—89°	C, 31.1 H, 3.3	31.1 3.3*
Chloralpropionamide	... $C_6H_9O_2NCl_2$	Alcohol	Thin plates	166—67°	Cl, 48.2	48.3
β -Dichlorovinylpropionamide	... $C_5H_7ONCl_2$	Benzene + ligroin	Needles	100—101°	C, 35.5 H, 4.3	35.7 4.2*
Chloral isobutyramide	... $C_6H_{10}O_2NCl_2$	Hot alcohol	Plates	156—57°	Cl, 45.3	45.4
β -Dichlorovinylisobutyramide	... $C_6H_9ONCl_2$	Dilute alcohol	Long needles	84—85°	38.8	39.0
Chloral-n-valeramide	... $C_7H_{12}O_2NCl_2$	Alcohol	Leaf like plates	142°	42.7	42.8
β -Dichlorovinyl-n-valeramide	... $C_7H_{11}ONCl_2$	Benzene + ligroin	Needles	65—66°	36.0	36.2
Chloral-n-capronamide	... $C_8H_{14}O_2NCl_2$	Alcohol	Shining plates	139°	40.4	40.5
β -Dichlorovinyl-n-capronamide	... $C_8H_{13}ONCl_2$	Benzene + ligroin	Needles	62—64°	33.7	33.8
Chloral-n-caprylamide	... $C_{10}H_{19}O_2NCl_2$	Hot alcohol	Plates	125—26°	36.6	36.7
β -Dichlorovinyl-n-caprylamide	... $C_{10}H_{17}ONCl_2$	Water	Needles	38—39°	29.6	29.8
β -Dichlorovinyl benzamide	... $C_9H_7ONCl_2$	Benzene + ligroin	Rectangular plates	68—70°	C, 49.8 H, 3.3	50.0 3.3*
Chloralphenylacetamide	... $C_{10}H_9O_2NCl_2$	Alcohol	Rhombic plates	141°	Cl, 37.5	37.7
β -Dichlorovinyl phenylacetamide	... $C_{10}H_8ONCl_2$	Alcohol	Long flat prisms	90—92°	30.5	30.8

* (cf. Yelburgi and Wheeler, loc. cit.).

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